

effects of Climatic extremes On eCOsystem Stability
COCOS

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (DCEP)

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Brief overview of research project and major accomplishments expected:

Extreme climatic events (hereafter, ECE) are climatic phenomena of exceptional intensity, such as extreme drought and heatwaves. Their frequency and magnitude are predicted to rise in the near future, as well as their negative impact on natural systems and on our societies. Indeed, ECE disrupt the stability of ecosystem functions and, as a result, the provisioning of ecosystem services important for human wellbeing (e.g., food production).

Within COCOS (effects of Climatic extremes On eCOsystem Stability), I will investigate the effect of ECE on the stability of key ecosystem functions such as plant biomass production. More specifically, I will analyse the capacity of different ecosystem types to buffer from ECE (i.e., resistance), and return to a reference level of functioning after ECE (i.e., recovery).

Analyses will account for the role of different biodiversity facets (i.e., taxonomic and functional) in supporting ecosystem resistance and recovery under extreme events, thereby improving knowledge on the biodiversity-stability relationship. Importantly, thanks to the availability of LOTVS, a global dataset of time-series of vegetation data, I will be able to test the association between ecosystem stability, biodiversity and ECE at a wide spatiotemporal scale.

Major **objectives (O)** related to COCOS are:

- providing predictions of resistance and recovery of different ecosystems to temperature and precipitation-related ECE (O1);
- assess whether and how different biodiversity components (i.e., taxonomic and functional) support ecosystems' resistance and recovery to ECE (O2);
- determine whether ECE induce critical transitions of ecosystem functions (O3).

Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan

A preliminary version of the dissemination, communication and exploitation plan was included in the project proposal (section 2.2). Building on that version, this document:

- Briefly recaps the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy underlying activities planned for COCOS;
- Lists the dissemination and communication activities already implemented (or partially implemented) at the time this DCEP was produced;
- Describes future dissemination, communication and exploitation activities to be implemented after the project's conclusion.

Strategy underlying dissemination, communication and exploitation activities within COCOS

Dissemination activities planned for COCOS were conceived to maximize the spread of research findings and project outcomes. Since the beginning of the project (October 2022), dissemination activities have combined participation in scientific conferences, joint symposia, seminars, and activity on social media, e.g. publication of posts and blog pieces documenting news and updates about COCOS. These activities primarily targeted an academic audience to foster exchange with researchers working on similar topics (e.g., extreme climatic events and ecosystem stability). For example, a seminar I presented at the University of Graz (see Act. 3

of the ‘Dissemination activities’ section) led to a collaboration with Prof. Clark, who is now actively involved in COCOS.

Since the beginning of the project, I have completed (or partially completed) most of the dissemination activities initially planned (see Table 1). As explained in the ‘Dissemination activities’ section (below), I will complete the remaining activities over the next two years. These include: the publication of a second scientific manuscript related to COCOS; the participation in a scientific conference to deliver the second oral presentation (scheduled before the project ends); and the production of a short animation video summarizing key findings from COCOS. Unlike most dissemination activities, the animation video will be directed to a wide, nonacademic audience.

Communication activities were originally designed to increase people’s awareness of the effects of climatic extremes on daily life and to inform a wide audience about COCOS. For this reason, these activities targeted a wide audience: not only academics but also policymakers and the general public. As an example, I gave an interview to a local Czech journal about COCOS and my experience as a Marie-Curie fellow in Czechia (see Act. 3 of the ‘Communication activities’ section). The interview was press-released and posted online to maximize its reach. Another example is my participation as an invited speaker at the Czech ‘National Information Day on Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions’, where I discussed COCOS research, my experience with writing the project proposal, and the pros and cons of leading a research project. The event was attended by researchers planning to apply for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) funding, evaluators of MSCA proposals, and experts in project writing and management. As for the dissemination activities, since the beginning of the project I completed almost all planned communication activities.

Both dissemination and communication activities were designed to comply with objectives and intents outlined in the ‘Open science practices’ and ‘Gender dimension and other diversity aspects’ sections of the MSCA project proposal. For example, concerning open science, I published a first scientific manuscript related to COCOS (<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.14288>) and associated programming scripts for reproducibility (<https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/620832781>) under a CC-BY 4.0 license. Concerning gender dimension and diversity inclusion, I attended conferences that oppose to discrimination for gender or other diversity aspects (e.g., the International Biogeography Society and the International Association for Vegetation Science). Additionally, I targeted all communication and dissemination activities to a gender-balanced and inclusive audience.

Concerning **exploitation activities**, COCOS will not generate outputs with commercial exploitation. However, I will produce analytical workflows, in the form of programming code (i.e., scripts), that I will keep improving and updating after the project ends. The scripts, which I will release through public GitHub and Zenodo repositories, will support future research on the relationship between ecosystem stability and extreme climatic events, and will contribute to the implementation of the European strategy on adaptation to climate change (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:82:FIN>).

Dissemination activities

Table 1 – Dissemination activities planned for COCOS (adapted from Table 3, section 2.2, of the project proposal). Column ‘Status’ reports whether activities were already implemented (**I**), partially implemented (**PI**) or yet to be implemented (i.e., to be implemented – **TBI**) at the time this DCEP was produced.

Activity	Channel	Aim	Audience	Status
1) Two scientific manuscripts	Open access journals	To disseminate research findings resulting from WP2 and WP3	Scientific	PI
2) Two oral presentations	Scientific conferences or joint symposia			PI
3) Two seminars	Seminar series	To show aims and methodology of COCOS		I
4) COCOS’ blog: <i>The fruits of COCOS</i>	COCOS webpage	To document COCOS’s findings or milestones achievement		I
5) Two animation videos (2-4 minutes)	COCOS’ YouTube channel	1) To disseminate COCOS’ research findings in plain English; 2) To provide younger generations with insights into COCOS’ findings	Wide	TBI

Overview of the dissemination activities already (or partially) implemented at the time this DCEP was produced:

Act. 1) Two scientific manuscripts: I published a first COCOS-related scientific manuscript entitled “*Biodiversity promotes resistance but dominant species shape recovery of grasslands under extreme drought*”. The manuscript was published open access in the [Journal of Ecology](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.14288) under a CC-BY 4.0 license (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.14288>). The article focused on the analysis of resistance and recovery of central European grasslands under extreme drought (Objective 1). Besides analyzing ecosystem’s resistance and recovery, I considered the role of multiple biodiversity facets in supporting the stability of plant biomass production (Objective 2).

Act. 2) Two oral presentations: I presented results from COCOS at two scientific symposia:

- Title: “*COCOS: effects of climatic extremes on ecosystem stability*”. 65th Symposium of the International Association for Vegetation Science, 3rd – 8th September 2023, Coffs Harbour, Australia. Oral communication;
- Title: “*Biodiversity-related mechanisms of ecosystem resistance under compound dry-hot extreme events*”. 11th Biennial Conference of the International Biogeography Society, 4th – 11th January 2024, Prague, Czech Republic. Poster communication. See Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Poster presented at the International Biogeography Society.

Act. 3) Two seminars: I participated in different seminar series to present COCOS research. Specifically, since the project started, I have presented three seminars at three different universities in three different European countries:

- Seminar at the Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (Host Institution): Title: “*Mediterranean coastal dunes, subantarctic islands and extreme climatic events: a vegetation ecology-based menu*”. Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, 24th November 2022, Prague, Czech Republic;
- Invited seminar at the University of Graz: Title: “*COCOS: effects of climatic extremes on ecosystem stability*”. University of Graz, 7th November 2023, Graz, Austria;
- Invited seminar at the University of Sassari: Title: “*COCOS: effects of climatic extremes on ecosystem stability*”. University of Sassari, 6th March 2024, Sassari, Italy. See Figure 2.

Figure 2 – COCOS seminar at the University of Sassari (Italy).

Act. 4) COCOS blog: At the beginning of the project, I created a webpage dedicated to COCOS. The webpage is hosted on my personal website (<https://mbazzichetto.netlify.app>) and can be accessed at the following link: <https://mbazzichetto.netlify.app/cocos/>. The page includes a description of COCOS (main research idea, tested ecological hypotheses, datasets used) and posts about the project, such as the publication of scientific manuscripts (see Act. 1 of this section) or my participation in conferences or similar events. I announced the creation of the COCOS webpage on my Twitter/X profile, and I also linked my personal website with all my social media accounts (Twitter/X, ResearchGate) to maximize its reach.

Overview of the dissemination activities yet to be implemented:

Act. 1) Two scientific manuscripts: I plan to publish a second scientific manuscript within 2025. This manuscript will present results on the analysis of ecosystem's resistance and recovery under compound dry-hot extreme events. Importantly, the article will focus on a much wider spatiotemporal scale than that considered in the first manuscript related to COCOS (see Act. 1 of the previous section).

Act. 2) Two oral presentations: I will give a second oral presentation at the 66th Annual Symposium of the International Association for Vegetation Science, which will be held from 16th to 20th September 2024 in Funchal, Madeira (Portugal) (<https://www.iavsportugal2024.com>). There, I will present results of the analyses on ecosystem's resistance and recovery under compound dry-hot extreme events, which will also be the focus of the second manuscript related to COCOS (see Act. 1 of this section).

Act. 5) Two animation videos: Within the next two years (i.e., within 2026), I plan to deliver at least one of the two animation videos mentioned in Table 1. So far, I have

not managed to produce the animation videos, as this activity is extremely time-consuming and requires long-term and close collaboration with a 3D animation expert (already identified in Dr. Alessandro Mattei; <https://vimeo.com/alessandromattei>).

Communication activities

Table 2 – Communication activities planned for COCOS (adapted from Table 3, section 2.2, of the project proposal). Column ‘Status’ reports whether activities were already implemented (I) or partially implemented (PI) at the time this DCEP was produced.

Activity	Channel	Aim	Audience	Status
1) Social media account	Twitter/X	To regularly provide news and updates about COCOS	Wide	I
2) Digital flyers	COCOS’ social media	To present aims and scope of COCOS	Wide	PI
3) Short blog pieces	Academic and press-related blogs	To raise awareness about the impact of extremes on our everyday life	Wide	I
4) Public talks	Environmental celebrations and research events	To document research and actions undertaken by COCOS to face the effect of extremes on ecosystems	Wide	I

Overview of the communication activities already implemented at the time this DCEP was produced:

Act. 1) Social media account: I posted about the start of COCOS on my Twitter/X and Mastodon profiles. These first posts (published on December, the 24th, 2024) aimed at briefly presenting the project and its main objectives (see post on Twitter/X at: <https://x.com/Mbazzichetto/status/1606594557961211906>). Subsequent activity on social media focused exclusively on Twitter/X, given the possibility of reaching a larger (and wider) audience. On Twitter/X, I mostly posted news and updates about COCOS, such as participation in conferences and publication of scientific articles. So far, I have published a total of 14 posts, which have collected an average of 19 likes, 4 retweets and 1.650 views (last update: 5th September 2024). All content that I published on Twitter/X included the #COCOS hashtag and tagged the @MSCAactions Twitter/X profile. This was done to increase visibility of the posts and to create a channel (through the use of the hashtag) where to easily find information about COCOS (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Examples of posts on Twitter/X published to, e.g., announce the start of the COCOS project (left) or to announce the publication of a blog post summarizing findings from the first COCOS-related manuscript.

Act. 3) Short blog pieces:

- I published a short piece on the blog of the [Journal of Ecology](#) where I summarized the main findings of the first manuscript related to COCOS (see Act. 1 of the ‘Dissemination activities’ section). To attract a nonacademic audience, I wrote the blog post in plain English (i.e., I avoided the use of scientific jargon). The blog post is freely accessible at the following link: <https://jecologyblog.com/2024/04/15/biodiversity-supports-grassland-resistance-and-recovery-under-extreme-drought/>;
- I was interviewed by the local Czech journal ‘*Pražský deník*’. The interview focused on COCOS and, more in general, on my experience as a MSCA fellow living in Czechia. The article was press-released and also published online on the website of the journal (https://prazsky.denik.cz/zpravy_region/praha-vedec-manuele-ceska-zemedelska-univerzita-rozhovor-20221214.html).

Act. 4) Public talks: I presented COCOS at two public events, which were attended by a wide audience:

- I was invited to give a talk at the Czech ‘National Information Day on Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions’, which was held online on April, the 12th, 2024. Besides quickly presenting COCOS, I talked about my experience with preparing the project proposal and I discussed the pros and cons of leading a MSCA project. My presentation targeted early career researchers who were planning to apply for MSCA funding. The event was attended by MSCA evaluators and experts in project writing and management. The full program of the event can be found at the following link: https://www.horizontevropa.cz/files_public/elfinder/5171/Programme_MSCA%20Information%20Day%202024.pdf;
- I participated in the 2024 EuroScience Open Forum, which was held from the 12th to the 15th of June 2024 in Katowice, Poland. There, I gave a talk about COCOS research at the thematic session: ‘*Climate Extremes, Ecosystem Dynamics, and Societal Implications in a Changing World-Insights from the MSCA Postdoctorate Fellowship Program*’. The aim of the session was to present examples of MSCA projects dealing with environmental sciences and ecology. The audience was mixed and consisted of students, academics, environmental policy-makers and journalists. The full program of the event can be accessed at the following link: https://irp.cdn-website.com/645376fd/files/uploaded/ESOF2024_Programme_14_may_2024.pdf.

Overview of the communication activities partially implemented:

- Act. 2) Digital flyers:** Although I did not produce the digital flyers at the outset of the project, I posted about COCOS on Twitter/X and created a dedicated webpage (see Act. 1 of the ‘Communication activities’ section and activity 4 of the ‘Dissemination activities’ section). These efforts served the same purpose as the digital flyers, i.e. presenting the research idea behind COCOS and its main objectives. Therefore, this activity can be considered partially implemented. I still plan to produce digital flyers highlighting key COCOS findings and to distribute them at future scientific symposia, such as the 67th Symposia of the International Association for Vegetation Science.

Exploitation activities

COCOS will not generate outputs with potential commercial exploitation. Rather, I will produce analytical workflows (in the form of reproducible programming code, hereafter scripts), which will support future research on the impact of climatic extremes on ecosystem's stability. Specifically, these scripts will allow researchers to quantify the temporal stability of ecosystem functions and/or estimate the intensity of extreme climatic events. Additionally, the scripts will allow deriving predictions of ecosystem's resistance and recovery under extreme climatic events.

Besides supporting future research, the analytical workflows generated within COCOS, as well as project findings on the relationship between ecosystem stability and climatic extremes, will contribute to the implementation of the European strategy on adaptation to climate change (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:82:FIN>). The strategy seeks to collect new data and knowledge on the effects of climatic extremes (smarter adaptation), and to design policies and management to minimize the impact of extremes on the society (systemic adaptation). In particular, COCOS would contribute with case studies (i.e., preprints and manuscripts) and tools (i.e., scripts) to enhance CLIMATE-adapt (<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en>), which is the European platform for adaptation knowledge.

I will release the scripts through public repositories created on my GitHub page (<https://github.com/ManueleBazzichetto>) within one year since the end of the project. Scripts will be released under a CC-BY 4.0 license. Importantly, I will keep improving and updating the scripts after the end of the project. Updated versions of the scripts will be published as new releases. To maximize dissemination and accessibility of the scripts, I will create and link Zenodo repositories to GitHub repositories. This way, repositories will be assigned a DOI. An example of this procedure (already implemented to share data and scripts related to the first COCOS manuscript) can be found at this link: <https://github.com/ManueleBazzichetto/ResistRecoverDrought>.